

Opinion

Adolescent PCOS: a postpubertal central obesity syndrome

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Adolescent polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is a highly prevalent, reversible, endocrine-metabolic mode essentially driven by ectopic fat, which, in turn, often results from a mismatch between early adipogenesis and later lipogenesis, or between prenatal and postnatal weight gain. The key features of adolescent PCOS are menstrual irregularity and androgen excess (hirsutism, acne, and/or high testosterone). Adolescent PCOS is frequently preceded by rapid maturation (early variants of adrenarche/pubarche and puberty/menarche, also accelerated by ectopic fat) and is diagnosed between 2 and 8 years after menarche, thus during late adolescence or early adulthood. Treatment of adolescent PCOS should not only focus on symptoms, but also reduce the amount of ectopic fat, thereby aiming for an overall state of preconception health.

Adolescent PCOS: from twilight to limelight

A quarter of a century ago, **adolescent PCOS** (see [Glossary](#)) was a vague entity in a twilight zone between late pediatrics and early gynecology, and between endocrinology and dermatology. Over the past decades, striking rises in the prevalence of overweight/obesity in girls have been accompanied by marked increases in the prevalences of rapid maturation and adolescent PCOS. These parallel developments have attracted scientific attention, which has led to an acceleration of our understanding of adolescent PCOS and its potential antecedents. Herein, we share new insights into developmental and evolutionary aspects of adolescent PCOS, and propose an update of diagnostic criteria and therapeutic approaches. In the years ahead, treatment of adolescent PCOS (and its antecedents) will be vital not only to improve preconception health to reduce gestational complications, but also to lower the elevated prevalences of adult PCOS (5–15%) [1,2] and its comorbidities, including type 2 diabetes, fatty liver disease, depression, and low health-related quality of life [3–7].

Adolescent PCOS: the end of a long beginning

Recent insights into the origins of the most common variants of adolescent PCOS discern at least three developmental steps ([Figure 1](#)).

The first step occurs during late prenatal and early postnatal life, and consists of the development of an upward percentile crossing (or ‘mismatch’) between (reduced) prenatal weight gain and (augmented) postnatal weight gain; that is, between early subcutaneous **adipogenesis** and later **lipogenesis**, or between the early capacity for safe lipid storage and the later need for lipid storage [8,9]. The higher the genetic susceptibility for obesity, the more gain of fat mass during infancy and, thus, the more risk for an upward mismatch [10]. A simple way of gauging such a mismatch is to calculate the upward change in percentiles between weight at birth and body mass index (BMI) in childhood [9,11]. Girls with an upward mismatch tend to store lipids in ectopic depots (mainly in liver and viscera) and, thus, tend to develop ‘**central obesity**’ with insulin resistance and higher blood pressure by early childhood (age 3–6 years) [12–14].

Highlights

Adolescent polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) has long been thought to be a gynecological disorder. However, emerging evidence suggests that it is not a disorder but a reversible, endocrine mode in response to ectopic fat. A simple way of screening for ectopic fat is to verify whether there has been an upward percentile crossing from weight at birth to body mass index (BMI) in adolescence.

Adolescent PCOS has so far been viewed as a disorder starting post menarche. The present view is that adolescent PCOS can only be understood by looking backward into early life: relatively high concentrations of circulating luteinizing hormone (LH), thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH), free T3, testosterone, dehydroepiandrosterone sulfate (DHEAS), and/or fasting insulin are reminiscent of a childhood wherein the same adaptive responses to ectopic fat enabled girls to accelerate their growth and maturation (with early pubarche/puberty/menarche) to outgrow their ectopic fatness and generate evolutionary fitness.

The definition of adolescent PCOS continues to be a matter of debate. We propose to merge the latest definitions of adolescent PCOS into a single set of diagnostic criteria.

Traditional treatment of adolescent PCOS focuses on symptoms. There is now evidence that treatment should also target ectopic fat and ultimately aim for preconception health.

The second step is activated during late childhood as an adaptive/homeostatic response to **ectopic fat**: mismatch girls accelerate their growth and maturation by concerted actions that include an amplification of adrenarche [higher levels of circulating dehydroepiandrosterone sulfate (DHEAS) possibly with **precocious pubarche** or early pubarche] [15–19], an upregulation of the gonadotropic axis [luteinizing hormone (LH) and estradiol, possibly with **precocious puberty** or early puberty] [20,21] and the thyroid axis [higher thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) and free T3] [22], more free testosterone [23], and an accelerated bone maturation [24]. Conversely, the percentiles of girls with precocious pubarche or precocious puberty tend to have been lower for weight at birth than for BMI at diagnosis, and, thus, to have crossed upward during early life (Figure 2, left and middle panels) [17–21]. The neuroendocrine mechanisms putatively linking ectopic fat to accelerated maturation have recently been reviewed elsewhere [25,26].

The third step in the ontogeny of adolescent PCOS occurs beyond menarche, when epiphysal fusion in the growth plates gradually impedes further height gain and, thus, the homeostatic effects of the growth-accelerating response to ectopic fat fade away. This step may explain why central obesity and associated rises in LH, TSH, DHEAS, and testosterone levels tend to rebound during the first postmenarcheal years, particularly in girls who grew and matured rapidly. PCOS is not a disorder but rather a reversible, endocrine-metabolic mode resulting from a concerted response to ectopic fat that is adaptive in growing girls but becomes maladaptive in grown-up adolescents. Henceforth, the PCOS acronym could stand for ‘Postpubertal Central Obesity

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Figure 1. The development of polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS; or Postpubertal Central Obesity Syndrome) is proposed to occur in three steps (for details, see the section ‘Adolescent PCOS: the end of a long beginning’ in the main text). Step 1 is completed during early life (upper-left textboxes). Step 2 is completed during late childhood and puberty (left columns in table). Step 3 is completed during adolescence and early adulthood (right column in table). The same endocrine responses to ectopic fat explain how a growth-accelerating solution in girls becomes a problem in adolescents and women: the initial presence and the subsequent absence of growth potential are pivotal. Abbreviations: DHEAS, dehydroepiandrosterone sulfate; LH, luteinizing hormone; TSH, thyroid-stimulating hormone.

Syndrome' [9]. Finally, the percentiles of adolescents and young women with PCOS also tend to have been lower for weight at birth than for BMI at diagnosis, and, thus, to have crossed upward during early life (Figure 2, right panel) [27–29].

Antecedents of adolescent PCOS versus the perception of an evolutionary paradox

The worldwide abundance of genetic susceptibility for PCOS has long been perceived as an evolutionary paradox because adult PCOS associates with anovulatory infertility and, thus, with a reproductive disadvantage [30–32]. However, this perception could be questioned for various reasons, as discussed below.

Antecedents of ancestral PCOS: from ectopic fatness to evolutionary fitness

In ancestral times, the late-childhood response to ectopic fat in mismatch girls may have conferred not only a survival advantage via a taller stature and a faster maturation, but also a reproductive advantage via a younger age of reproduction, thereby abbreviating the timespan between generations. In this context, one reminder: upward-mismatch girls with incipient PCOS have normal ovulation rates during early adolescence, but lower rates from late adolescence onward [33]. Thus, from early adulthood onward, PCOS may have acted as a natural post-reproductive contraceptive that enhanced the survival of young mothers by lowering their subsequent risk for gestational/obstetric complications.

Ancestral PCOS: a milder phenotype with less impact on reproductive success

In ancestral times, the environment must have been less obesogenic than it is now; thus, there would have been less pressure to enter into a strikingly upward birthweight-to-BMI mismatch [30,32]. Therefore the average phenotype of ancestral PCOS is likely to have been milder, with less impact on overall reproductive success, and, thus, is unlikely to have generated a strong selection [30,32].

When and how to diagnose adolescent PCOS

The diagnostic criteria of adolescent PCOS have long been a matter of debate, mainly because some PCOS features in women may still be part of a normal maturation in adolescent girls [2]. At present, the established key features of adolescent PCOS are menstrual irregularity and androgen excess [34–36], and the debate is limited to the specifics of these key features.

Diagnostic guidelines: from two perspectives to one consensus

Table 1 summarizes the diagnostic criteria as recently phrased by two international consortia, one of them being rooted in fetal, neonatal, pediatric, and adolescent endocrinology, thus looking forward into preconception health and adult PCOS [34], and the other being rooted in adult endocrinology, gynecology and reproductive medicine, thus looking backward into adolescence but not necessarily further backward into puberty, childhood, infancy, and prenatal life [35–38].

Risk of overdiagnosis and overtreatment in younger girls was a major concern in the forward-looking consortium (Table 1, left column) the criteria of which were more restrictive than those of the backward-looking consortium (Table 1, middle column). Both sets of diagnostic criteria are now tested and, in particular, the strict requirement of clinical and biochemical androgen excess is perceived as too stringent by the new **SPIOMET4HEALTH consortium**, which focuses on adolescent PCOS.[†] This perception is largely based on the fact that testosterone assays whereby biochemical androgen excess is screened in daily practice present elevated interassay variability, and also on the fact that no clear cut-off level of circulating testosterone has so far been defined to diagnose adolescent PCOS [2,34–38]. Therefore, we propose to merge the two sets of

Glossary

Adipogenesis: development of adipose tissue, notably including the differentiation of adipocytes from precursor cells.

Adolescent polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS): PCOS between 2 and 8 years after menarche.

Central obesity: fat excess in the abdominal area, particularly in ectopic depots.

Cycle: timespan between menses.

Ectopic fat: triglyceride accumulation in normally lean organs (e.g., liver) and in normally small lipid depots (e.g., visceral adipose tissue).

Ferriman–Gallwey score (modified): method of quantifying hirsutism (in nine body areas).

Free androgen index (FAI): equivalent to circulating concentrations of free, biologically active testosterone.

Hirsutism: excess of terminal hair in androgen-dependent areas.

Lipogenesis: synthesis of fatty acids and triglycerides for storage, mainly in adipocytes of adipose tissue and in the liver.

Oligomenorrhea: infrequent menses (see Table 1 in the main text for specific criteria).

Precocious pubarche in girls: appearance of pubic hair before age 8 years.

Precocious puberty in girls: start of breast development before age 8 years.

SPIOMET: a low-dose combination of spironolactone (50 mg/d), pioglitazone (7.5 mg/d), and metformin (850 mg/d).

SPIOMET4HEALTH consortium: international group of investigator teams participating in a multicentric, randomized, double-blind clinical trial documenting the effects of lifestyle intervention plus either pioglitazone (PIO), or spironolactone-and-pioglitazone (SPIO), or SPIOMET in patients with adolescent PCOS.[†]

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Figure 2. Upward percentile crossing ('mismatch') from weight at birth to body mass index (BMI) at diagnosis in girls with precocious pubarche (left panel), precocious puberty (middle panel), or polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS; right panel). Mean weight at birth is expressed in percentiles for sex and gestational age. Mean BMI at diagnosis is expressed in percentiles for sex and postnatal age. Girls with rapid maturation and/or PCOS tend to have experienced an upward mismatch between prenatal and postnatal weight gain. Weight at birth tends to be average in study cohorts with obesity, and to be below average in study cohorts without obesity. Data from [17–21,25–27].

recommended criteria into one diagnostic consensus (Table 1, right column), the application of which has already been endorsed by the SPIOMET4HEALTH consortium.

Menstrual irregularity: what is (ab)normal?

Most adolescent girls establish regular **cycles** within the first 2 years after menarche. Irregular cycles can be physiological up to 2 years after menarche; in most of these cases, cycles become regular (21–35 days) shortly after year 2. In the minority with persistently irregular menses, there is an indication to screen for androgen excess since this irregularity is a clinical proxy of oligo-anovulation [34–38]. However, a fraction of older adolescents with irregular menses do still ovulate [39].

Menstrual irregularity in adolescent PCOS has been defined (Table 1, left column) as dysfunctional bleeding, **oligomenorrhea**, or secondary amenorrhea; only a small fraction present with primary amenorrhea after completed puberty [2,34]. Subsequently, menstrual irregularity has also been graded by years elapsed since menarche (Table 1, middle column) [35–38]. In the present proposal (Table 1, right column), we maintain the original definition, in part because it is more simple to use in adolescent clinics, and because it ensures a longer maturation time for the gonadotropic axis of younger adolescents, thereby providing additional protection against overdiagnosis and overtreatment [40].

Oligomenorrhea in adolescence is known to associate with not only a higher BMI and androgen excess, but also with PCOS in adulthood [41,42]. Accordingly, some guidelines recommend the

Table 1. Diagnostic criteria for adolescent PCOS (up to 8 years post menarche)^a

Criteria of a consortium rooted in fetal, neonatal, pediatric, and adolescent endocrinology, thus looking forward into preconception health ^{b,c} [32]	Criteria of a consortium rooted in adult endocrinology and gynecology, thus looking backward into adolescence ^{b,c} [33]	Proposed merging of the two sets of previously recommended criteria into one diagnostic consensus ^{b,c}
Menstrual irregularity		
>2 years post menarche: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cycles <21 days (dysfunctional bleeding) • Cycles >45 days (oligomenorrhea) • Secondary amenorrhea (no menses for >90 days) • Primary amenorrhea after completed growth/puberty 	Postmenarche <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1–3 years: cycles <21 or >45 days • >3 years: cycles <21 or >35 days, or <8 cycles/year • >1 year: any cycle >90 days • Primary amenorrhea at 15 years or >3 years post-B2 	> 2 years post menarche: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cycles <21 days (dysfunctional bleeding) • Cycles >45 days (oligomenorrhea) • Secondary amenorrhea (no menses for >90 days) • Primary amenorrhea after completed growth/puberty
Androgen excess		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clinical: modified Ferriman–Gallwey score ≥5–6 ‘and’ • Biochemical: high testosterone (LC-MS/MS) or FAI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clinical: modified Ferriman–Gallwey score ≥4–6 ‘and/or’ • Biochemical: high testosterone (LC-MS/MS) or FAI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clinical: modified Ferriman–Gallwey score ≥4–6 ‘and/or’ • Biochemical: high testosterone (LC-MS/MS) or FAI

^aAbbreviation: B2, Tanner breast stage 2.

^bOther causes of androgen excess, such as adrenal hyperplasia, adrenal or ovarian tumor, cortisol or prolactin excess, were excluded.

^cNone of the diagnostic sets required an assessment of ovarian morphology, insulin resistance, or circulating anti-Müllerian hormone.

customary follow-up of adolescents with menstrual irregularity, considered ‘at risk’ for PCOS, particularly if overweight or obese [36].

Evaluation of clinical and biochemical androgen excess

Hirsutism, acne, and seborrhea are the key clinical markers of androgen excess in girls. In adolescent PCOS, hirsutism is typically moderate to severe and slowly progressive, and is normally assessed by a modified version of the original **Ferriman–Gallwey score** [43,44]. There is a consensus that a score of 6 or more is abnormal [34–38] but a score of 4 or more may already point to androgen excess in girls of northern European or Asian descent [35,36], and, therefore, the lower cut-off is included in the proposed update of the diagnostic criteria for adolescent PCOS (Table 1, right column). Population studies have linked higher hirsutism scores to higher levels of circulating testosterone [41,45]. Rapidly progressive hirsutism and/or signs of virilization point to an androgen-secreting tumor, adrenal hyperplasia, or an exogenous source of androgens [2,34].

Biochemical androgen excess is screened by measuring the total concentration of circulating testosterone, preferably by liquid chromatography with tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS); calculation of the **free androgen index** (FAI), an equivalent of free testosterone [FAI = testosterone (nmol/l) × 100/sex hormone binding globulin (SHBG) (nmol/l)] is also recommended [34–36,45,46] (Table 1). These measurements should be performed during the follicular phase or after 2 months of amenorrhea, and in the absence of hormonal contraception for >3 months [36]. The cut-off values vary by assay and method, but a testosterone level >1.4 nmol/l and/or a FAI >3.5 points to androgen excess [34,45]. Isolated hyperandrogenemia is present in ~1% of adolescents with regular cycles [45], and those girls are also considered ‘at risk’ for subsequent PCOS [36]. Extremely high levels of testosterone (>5.2 nmol/l) or DHEAS (>19 μmol/l) suggest the presence of an ovarian or adrenal androgen-secreting tumor. A basal 17-hydroxy-progesterone level <6 nmol/l excludes 21-hydroxylase deficiency [34–36].

Treatment of adolescent PCOS: targeting ectopic fat and aiming for preconception health

At present, there is still no approved treatment for adolescent PCOS. The most widely recommended treatments are oral estrogen-progestogen contraceptives (OCs), which silence the

gonadotropic axis (including ovulatory function), elicit regular pseudo-menses, and reduce androgen excess in part via pharmacological upregulation of SHBG [35,37,38]. This ensemble may be far from physiological but it has long been perceived as an acceptable outcome that is readily achievable at relatively low cost and risk [35,37,38]. Worldwide, such off-label treatments have been, and are still being, prescribed for millions of adolescents with PCOS (even for young ‘at risk’ girls who do not need contraception) without studying the effects on post-treatment ovulation rate or preconception health. Given the novel premise that ectopic fat is a prevalent driver of adolescent PCOS and also a potential perpetuator into adult PCOS, we propose that ectopic fat should be the core target of intervention [8,9], and that optimization of preconception health should be the ultimate aim [47].

Lifestyle measures: the first-line treatment for adolescent PCOS

Lifestyle intervention requires a multidisciplinary approach that ensures a healthy diet, regular exercise and sleep, and respect for biorhythms [48–50]. Such a sustained lifestyle intervention has normalizing effects on circulating androgens, insulin resistance, cardiovascular risk factors, and reproductive health outcomes [27,51]. Reducing body weight by 5% may suffice to improve metabolic state and menstrual regularity [52]. Caloric intake should target moderate weight loss when needed, and weight maintenance when appropriate. Liver fat can be reduced and lean mass can be augmented by switching any lipid intake from saturated to polyunsaturated fatty acids [53]. Replacing red meat by other proteins improves biomarkers of inflammation and glucose turnover, and may thereby confer metabolic benefits [54]. Sleep hygiene is recommended since poor sleep and circadian misalignment are associated with unfavorable metabolic profiles [49,50]. Mendelian randomization studies have disclosed that a shorter sleep duration is a risk factor for ectopic adiposity [55]. Lifestyle measures are notoriously difficult to maintain and, thus, their longer-term efficacy may be limited, thereby highlighting the need to add a pharmacological intervention.

Pharmacological treatment for adolescent PCOS: an unmet need

Research is focusing on the development of medications that lead to a preferential loss of ectopic fat.

PCOS girls with obesity: reducing ectopic fat by lowering body weight

In girls with obesity, a promising line of research has focused on weight loss. Among the new drugs tested are glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) agonists, such as liraglutide and semaglutide. GLP-1 agonists mimic the anorexigenic effects of GLP-1, an incretin that regulates energy homeostasis. These compounds have been proven to be effective in reducing body adiposity in patients with obesity and without PCOS [56,57]. In adolescents with obesity, lifestyle intervention plus liraglutide or semaglutide reduce BMI more than lifestyle intervention alone [58,59]; at present, only liraglutide has been approved for treatment of obesity in patients aged 12 years or older with risk factors. In women with PCOS, GLP-1 agonists decrease body weight and improve androgen excess, metabolic markers, and reproductive function [60,61]; these findings further corroborate the concept that ectopic fat is the key force driving PCOS. In adolescents with obesity and PCOS, there is an ongoing clinical trial comparing the effects of diet versus semaglutideⁱⁱ.

PCOS girls without obesity: reducing ectopic fat by repartitioning fat storage

In adolescents with PCOS and without obesity, a longstanding line of research has focused on fat repartitioning from ectopic to normal depots. The expandability of subcutaneous adipose tissue tends to be limited in these patients [8,9], secondary, for example, to prenatal growth restraint (which is of particular relevance for South Asian populations), to a partial lipodystrophy [62], or to a genetic variation that restricts gluteofemoral adipogenesis and, thus, gynoid adipose tissue [63].

Clinician's corner

- PCOS is a common cause of androgen excess in adolescent girls. Girls with an upward mismatch between pre- and postnatal weight gain are at higher risk for developing PCOS.
- The diagnosis of adolescent PCOS is based on the combination of (i) clinical and/or biochemical androgen excess; and (ii) menstrual irregularity in girls who are at least 2 years beyond menarche. Up to 8 years after menarche, a PCOS diagnosis is independent of ovarian morphology or circulating anti-Müllerian hormone.
 - Clinically, hirsutism is considered evidence of androgen excess and is graded by the modified Ferriman–Gallwey score. A score of 6 or more is high for White girls, but a score 4 or more is high for Asian or Northern European girls.
 - Biochemically, high testosterone and/or high FAI are indicative of androgen excess. Menstrual irregularities suggest a low ovulation rate, and can present as oligomenorrhea (cycles >45 days), secondary amenorrhea (no menses for >3 months), or frequent uterine bleeding (cycles <21 days). A small fraction of girls present with completed puberty and primary amenorrhea.
 - Diagnosis of PCOS requires the exclusion of alternative causes of androgen excess and/or menstrual irregularity, such as thyroid dysfunction, hyperprolactinemia, congenital adrenal hyperplasia, or an androgen-secreting tumor.
- There is no approved treatment for adolescent PCOS.
 - The focus should be a reduction of ectopic fat, starting with a healthy lifestyle that combines a variety of measures related to exercise, diet, sleep, and biorhythm.
- In girls with obesity, weight-loss medications, such as GLP-1 agonists are under investigation.

So far, the most promising results have been obtained with a low-dose combination of three medications that act through different pathways: spironolactone, pioglitazone, and metformin (SPIOMET) [64,65]. Spironolactone (only 50 mg/day) has long been used as an anti-androgen [34–38] but may be particularly helpful as an anti-mineralocorticoid that can raise the low activity of brown adipose tissue in adolescents with PCOS and without obesity, thereby also augmenting their energy expenditure and facilitating their control of body weight [66–68]. In adolescents with PCOS and without obesity, pioglitazone (only 7.5 mg/day) can double the circulating concentrations of high-molecular-weight adiponectin (perhaps by stimulating subcutaneous adipogenesis), which is an adipokine that reduces ectopic fat (notably in the liver) and thereby decreases insulin resistance [64,69,70]. In adolescents with PCOS and without obesity, metformin (only 850 mg/day) exerts normalizing effects through multiple mechanisms [71], one of which may be a tripling of the circulating concentrations of growth- and- differentiation factor 15 (GDF15) [72], a peptide hormone that tends to reduce appetite by acting through a specific brainstem-restricted receptor [73,74]. Randomized, open-label, single-center pilot studies recently compared the effects of an OC versus SPIOMET treatment in adolescents with PCOS and without obesity [65,75–77]; SPIOMET appeared to reverse the entire

- In girls without obesity and without need for contraception, a low-dose combination of SPIOMET is under investigation. Available evidence suggests that SPIOMET leads to an overall state of preconception health, which, in turn, may lower the risk for gestational complications.
- If such longer-term focus is not possible, then administration of an oral estrogen-progestin contraceptive is traditionally recommended. This treatment can swiftly attenuate gynecological and dermatological symptoms, but does not solve the root problem of ectopic fat and its endocrine correlates.

Key figure

Divergent responses to an ovary-silencing treatment (with an oral estrogen-progestin contraceptive (OC)) versus an ectopic fat-reducing intervention (with spironolactone, pioglitazone and metformin (SPIOMET))

Figure 3. Longitudinal results (mean ± SEM) of circulating thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH), the hepatic fat fraction (by magnetic resonance imaging), and the mean serum insulin (MSI) Z-score during an oral glucose tolerance test in adolescent girls with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) and without obesity, who were randomized to receive either an OC or SPIOMET for 1 year (shaded area), and who were subsequently followed for 1 year without treatment. The post-treatment number of ovulations was assessed by weekly measurements of salivary progesterone during the second and fourth quarters of the post-treatment year, and were then annualized. The dashed line represents the average values in healthy controls of similar age. TSH, hepatic fat, and MSI results were elevated at baseline, and were more normalized with SPIOMET than with OC, as well during treatment as after treatment. The post-treatment number of ovulations was 2.8-fold higher after SPIOMET than after OC treatment. Data from [65,67].

PCOS phenotype, virtually without changing body weight (see [Clinician's corner](#)); between-subgroup divergences were consistently to the advantage of SPIOMET (Figure 3, Key figure). These data prompted the initiation of a randomized, double-blind, multicenter study (NCT05394142) that is testing, on top of lifestyle measures, the contribution of each SPIOMET component to the overall benefits of this potentially new polypill for adolescent PCOS.

Prevention of PCOS: where do we stand?

Girls with a mismatch between prenatal and postnatal weight gain are at risk for developing PCOS [78]. Prevention of such outcome includes moderation of the catch-up in weight from early childhood onward. In mismatch girls with low birthweight and rapid maturation (early pubarche/puberty/menarche), the prolonged intake of metformin may be helpful to prevent or delay PCOS, even in the absence of obesity [79–81]. In mismatch girls with early puberty, the effects of half-dose SPIOMET are under investigation [82].

Concluding remarks

We are confident that finding answers to our outstanding questions (see [Outstanding questions](#)) will open new perspectives in the years ahead. One of the many items not discussed here is the potential value of new tools that can enhance the communication between adolescents with PCOS and their healthcare providers. Such tools might be helpful in the development of novel Patient-Reported Outcome Measures that assess the quality of care from the patient's perspective, and might also contribute to counteract the impact of PCOS on emotional, social, and physical functioning, and, thus, on health-related quality of life.

We close by paraphrasing a famous verse written by Rudyard Kipling: 'if you can meet with early puberty and adolescent PCOS [instead of 'if you can meet with Triumph and Disaster'], and treat those two impostors just the same'. Indeed, early puberty and adolescent PCOS are two impostors since both masquerade as upregulation disorders of the gonadal axis, whereas they are, in most cases, no more than endocrine-metabolic responses to ectopic fat; these responses are adaptive in growing girls with rapid maturation but become maladaptive in grown-up adolescents with PCOS. Recent guidelines [35,83] still suggest to 'treat those two impostors just the same', namely by silencing the gonadotropic axis (with a gonadotropin-releasing hormone analog in girls, and with an OC in adolescents), whereas both groups should be treated primarily by reducing ectopic fat.

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Declaration of interests

The authors have nothing to disclose.

Resources

www.spiomet4health.eu

<https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/NCT03919929>

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Outstanding questions

Which will be the next genetic and epigenetic factors to be shown to be involved in the development of PCOS in ethnically and phenotypically diverse populations?

Clinical evidence for the development of human PCOS remains to be further aligned with experimental evidence in so-called animal models of PCOS, many of which are based on prenatal androgen excess. Can clinical and experimental evidence be integrated through studies of adipogenesis, keeping in mind that the fraction of subcutaneous fat in newborn girls is much higher than in the mammalian PCOS models so far studied?

Will earlier, more predictive, more readily accessible, and more affordable biomarkers of PCOS (and its antecedents) soon be identified?

Treatments should be further explored in prepubertal or early-pubertal girls with PCOS antecedents: for example, combinations of a healthier diet (Mediterranean? Vegetarian? Less meal skipping? Intermittent fasting?), more exercise, longer sleep, and low-dose 'polypills' with old and safe medications (metformin? spironolactone?).

Will clinicians be prepared to pay as much attention to the treatment of the core problem of ectopic fat in adolescent girls with PCOS as to the treatment of gynecological and dermatological symptoms?

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